

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.3.1.6: Landscape and seascape degradation

Version: 2

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5533042

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Description

Section 3.3.1.6 assesses the role of landscape and seascape degradation as drivers of biological invasions in Chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Search 2:

Search 3:

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

Search 1: ("land degradation" OR "seascape degradation" OR "disturbance") AND (degradation OR salinization OR desertification OR erosion OR overgrazing) AND (invasive OR alien OR exotic OR non-native OR non indigenous) AND (review OR "systematic review" OR "meta-analysis" OR "meta analysis" OR "literature review" OR "synthesis" OR "synthesis matrix")

Search 2: (degrad* OR disturb*) AND (salinization OR desertification OR erosion OR overgrazing) AND (invasive OR alien OR exotic OR non-native OR non indigenous) AND (review OR "meta-analysis" OR synthesis)

Search 3: (invasive OR alien OR exotic OR non-native OR non indigenous) with some specific keywords (e.g., grazing, disturbance-invasion hypothesis)

- Search engine:

Search 1: Web of science

Search 2 and 3: Google scholar

- Date:

Search 1: 19 September 2019

Search 2: 20 September 2019

Search 3: 25 September 2019

- Overview of the search results and selection criteria:

Number of search result:

Search 1:0

Search 2:6

Search 3:10

Selection criteria:

Search 1: Searched with above terms, then refined by excluding low relevant papers by experts' knowledge.

Search 2: Searched with above terms, then refined by excluding low relevant papers from Top 100 papers by experts' knowledge.

Search 3: Searched with above terms, then refined by excluding low relevant papers by experts' knowledge.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 11

- Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):

Number of papers reviewed: 27 (See [Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#))

Fields extracted:

- Publication title

- Year of publication

- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]

- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]

- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]

- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]

- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]

- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]

-Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]

-Comment (free text)

- Files (code, review templates, etc.):

[Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#)